

Specific Features of Compound Nouns in English and Uzbek Languages

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Annotation:

A compound is a word composed of more than one free morpheme. English compounds may be classified in several ways, such as the word classes or the semantic relationship of their components.

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Compound nouns are nouns built from two or more stems. Compound nouns often have stress. The meaning of a compound often differs from the meanings of its elements.

The structural cohesion and integrity of a compound may depend upon unity of stress, solid or hyphenated spelling, semantic unity, unity of morphological and syntactic functioning or, more often, upon the combined effect of several of these or similar phonetic, graphic, semantic, morphological or syntactic factors.

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Examples by word class

Modifier	Head	Compound
Noun +	Noun =	wall paper
Adjective +	Noun =	black board
Verb +	Noun =	break water
Preposition +	+ Noun =	under world
Noun +	Adjective	= snow white
Adjective +	Adjective	= blue – green

Verb	+	Adjective =	tumbledown
Preposition +		Adjective =	over – ripe
Noun +		Verb =	Browbeat
Adjective +		Verb =	Highlight
Verb +		Verb =	freeze – dry
Preposition +		Verb =	Undercut
Noun +		Preposition	= love – in
Adjective +		Preposition	= forth with
Verb +		Preposition	= take out
Preposition +		Preposition	= Without

Uzbek compounds are short compounds.

Ex: ko‘zoynak, atirgul, bo‘tako‘z, toqqaychi.

The way of forming Uzbek and English short compounds are the same. There are three ways of forming short compounds

1. The solid or closed form in which two usually moderately short words appear together as one. Solid compounds most likely consists of short (monosyllabic) units that often have been established in the language for a long time. Examples are; housewife, lawsuit, and wallpaper. Uzbek examples are: suvilon, tog‘olcha, gultuvak.

2. The hyphenated form in which two or more words are connected by a hyphen . Compounds that contain affixes , such as house – builder and single – mind (ed) (ness) but if these words are written in Uzbek they will be written without hyphen: single – mindedness – хурфикрлилик.

As well as adjective - adjective compounds and verb – verb compounds, such as blue – green and freeze – dry, are often hyphenated. Some Uzbek verb – verb compounds are also hyphenated: sotib - oldi, borib - keldi.

Compounds that contain particles, such as mother – of – pearl and salt – and – pepper, mother – in – law, merry – go – round, are also hyphenated.

3. The open or spaced form consisting of newer combinations of usually longer, such as: distance learning, player piano, lawn tennis. In Uzbek there are also such kind of open compounds: stol tennisi, masofaviy o‘qitish.

Some compounds are made up of a determining and a determined part, which may be called the determinant and determinate group. Thus, a chatterbox – оташқалб is not a box, it is a person who talks a great deal without saying anything important: the combination is used only figuratively. The same metaphorical character is observed in the compound slowcoach - xomsemiz. It is also idiomatic as it does not name a vehicle but a person who acts and thinks slowly

A compound word possesses a single semantic structure. The meaning of the compound is first of all derived from the combined lexical meanings of its components, which as a rule; retain their lexical meanings, although their semantic range becomes considerably narrowed. The lexical meanings of the components are closely fused together to create a new semantic unit with a new meaning that is not merely additive but dominates the individual meanings of the components. The semantic centre of the compound is found in the lexical meaning of the second component which is modified and restricted by the lexical meaning of the first, e.g. **hand-bag** is essentially 'a **bag** carried in the hand for money, papers, face-powder, etc.'; **pencil-case** is 'a case for pencils', etc.

The components are often stems of polysemantic words but there is no difficulty, as a rule, of defining which of the multiple denotational meanings the stem retains in one or another compound word. Compound words with a common second component can serve as an illustration. Let us take words with a common second component, e.g. **board-Board** - is the stem of a polysemantic word but it retains only one of its multiple denotational meanings in each compound word: in **chess-board** it retains the denotational meaning of 'a wooden slab', in **pasteboard**, **cardboard** it can be traced to the meaning of 'thick, stiff paper', in **overboard** to 'a ship's side', in **notice-board**, **foot-board**, **key-board** to 'a flat piece of wood square or oblong'; in **school-board** to 'an authorized body of men', in **side-board**, **above-board** to the meaning of 'table'. The same can be observed in words with a common first component, e.g. **foot-**, in **foot-high**, **foot-wide** the stem **foot** - retains the lexical meaning of 'measure'; in **foot-print**, **foot-pump**, **foot-hold** —'the terminal part of the leg'; in **foot-path**, **foot-race** the meaning of 'the way of motion'; in **foot-note**, **foot-lights**, **foot-stone** —'the meaning of 'the lower part, base'. It is obvious from these examples that the meanings of the stems of compound words are interdependent and in each case the stems retain only one lexical meaning and that the choice of the particular lexical meaning of each component is delimited, as in free word-groups, by the nature of the other member of the word. Thus we may say that the combination of stems serves as a kind of minimal context distinguishing the particular individual lexical meaning of each component.

Both components, besides their denotational and connotational meanings possess distributional and differential types of meaning typical of morphemes the differential meaning, found in both components especially comes to the fore in a group of compound words containing identical stems. In compound nouns **eye-tooth** —'a canine tooth of the upper jaw', **eye-lash** —'the fringe of hair that edges the eyelid', **eye-witness** —'one who can bear witness from his own observation', **eye-glasses** —'a pair of lens used to assist defective sight', **eye-sore** —'an ugly or unpleasant thing to see', **eye-strain** —'weariness of the eye', etc. it is the differential meaning of the second components—**tooth-**, **glasses-**, **witness-**, etc. that brings forth -the different lexical meanings of the stem **.eye** - and serves as a distinguishing clue between these words. We observe a similar significance of the differential meaning for the choice of the lexical meaning of the other component in words with the identical second component. In compound words, e.g. **wedding-ring**, **nose-ring**, **ear-ring**, **finger-ring**, **key-ring**, **circus-ring**, **prize-ring**, etc., it is not only the denotational but mostly the differential meaning of **nose-**, **ear-**, **finger-**, etc. that distinguishes **wedding-ring** —'a ring worn constantly as a distinctive mark of a married woman' from **ear-ring** —'an ornament worn in the lobe of ear', **key-ring** — 'a ring for keeping keys on', **circus-ring** —'an arena in a circus' and **prize-ring** —'an enclosed area for fighting'.

The component of Uzbek compounds are combined in this way:

1. Phonetical changes in the first components of compound words. The consonants in the beginning of the first component may be changed into another component:

Ex: sichqoncho‘p - tishqoncho‘p (the names of plant)

chilonjiyda – jilonjiyda

soztuproq - sog‘tuproq

In some compounds suffixes may be omitted and may form variants of the compounds words.

Ex: tugmachagul - tugmagul (“cha” is omitted)

gadoytaxlit - gadotaxlit (“y” is omitted.)

ayta olmaslik – aytolmaslik

bo‘la olmaslik - bo‘lolmaslik

In compound word is ended with “yo”, it must be written separately if it is ended with “yo” it must be written together as one word.

Ex: qishlay olmoq - qishlayolmoq

ushlay olmoq - ushlayolmoq

to‘qiy olmoq - to‘qiyolmoq

To form a compound verb with the verbs “yemoq, demoq” which have “e” sound in the root, one must add “ya (y + a)” after “e, de” e. g.: de+ya olmoq – deyaolmoq, ye+ya olmoq, eya olmoq.

2. Phonetical changes in the second components of compound words. Ex: itburun - itmurun
Tuyabo‘yin - Tuyamo‘yin.

“b” consonant in the beginning of the second component a changed into “v”

Ex: qoraboy – qoravoy, qo‘ziboy- qo‘zivoy

amakibachcha - amakivachcha, tog‘abachcha - tog‘avachcha.

A compound word has a single semantic structure. We distinguish the meaning of the compound words from the combined lexical meaning of its components. Ex: “pencil-case” is a case for pencils. A change in the order of components of compound words brings a change in the lexical meaning.

Ex: life-boat – “a boat of special construction for saving lives. Boat-life – life on board of a ship.

Compound words are classified into completely motivated partially motivated and non-motivated compound words”.

The compound words “a flower-bed, walk-up are partially motivated compounds because we can guess their meaning partially”. The compounds in which the connection between the meaning and structure and the meanings of components of compounds can seen from the meaning of its components are called non-motivated compound words. Ex: wall-flower – a woman who remains at wall and is not invited to a dance.

Like other linguistic phenomena we may approach to the study of compounds synchronically and diachronically. Synchronically we study the structural and semantic patterns of compound words while diachronically we study the various changes compound words undergone on the course of time and the way compound words appear in the language.

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